

D6.1: Initial Dissemination Plan: update

Author:

Barbara Morganti

Contributors:

Holly Wright, Kate Fernie, Tom Usher, Carol Usher, all partners

Version: 1.0

LoCloud is funded by the European Commission's
ICT Policy Support Programme

Change Log

Version	Date	Amended by	Changes
V.01 -draft	09-06.2013	Kate Fernie (MDR)	Outline
V.02 -draft	30-06-2013	Barbara Morganti (MDR)	First draft
V.02 -draft	08-07-2013	Barbara Morganti (MDR)	Various amendments to take into account Kate Fernie's and Rob Davies' comments
V1.0-final	08-08-2013	Barbara Morganti (MDR), Kate, Fernie (MDR)	Final revision
V2.0	08-10-2014	Barbara Morganti (NRA)	Update for second project period

Table of Contents

1. Executive summary	4
2. Objectives	5
3. Responsibilities for dissemination activities	6
4. Stakeholder community	7
4.1 Internal stakeholders	7
4.2 Small and medium sized institutions	8
4.3 Research community and cloud computing companies / providers.....	9
4.4 European Commission.....	9
4.5 Clustering with other projects	10
4.6 Groups and associations.....	10
4.7 Stakeholder database.....	11
5. Dissemination materials	12
5.1 Project logo.....	12
5.2 Project website.....	12
5.3 Project newsletter.....	13
5.4 Other dissemination materials.....	13
5.5 Acknowledgement of EU funding.....	14
6. Dissemination channels	15
6.1 Project web site and partners web sites	15
6.2 Mailing lists.....	15
6.3 Social networks.....	16
6.4 Press releases.....	17
17	
7. Dissemination activities	18
7.1 Potential national and international events.....	18
7.2 Potential Journals.....	26
7.2 LoCloud planned events.....	29
8. Conclusion	30
9. Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines	31
10. Appendix II: Guidelines for partners	32

1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents a dissemination strategy for the **LoCloud project** and it covers months 1 to 24 of the project.

LoCloud will support small and medium-sized institutions in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by exploring the potential of cloud computing technologies. The project will work on a cloud-based technology infrastructure that will enable the aggregation of local content. It will also develop a number of micro-services to help to reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers and to render the content more discoverable and interoperable.

The aims of the dissemination strategy are to raise awareness about the LoCloud project and its activities amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations.
- Organisations with an interest in cloud computing, applied to small and medium sized institutions, including small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, holders of private collections, and others.
- The Research Community with an interest and involvement in cloud computing in general, and to cultural institutions in particular.
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme.
- Europeana, members of the general public, students, researchers, etc.

The objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Identify the interests of the stakeholder community and the main channels for communication and networking activities.
- Build and extend the project contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts.
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media.
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, briefing papers, presentation template, and other materials for use by the partners.
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

This plan is an updated version of the first Initial dissemination plan and will inform dissemination activities during the second project period. The plan will feed into the Interim dissemination report at month 24 and will be updated in this document to plan activities for the final project period. In this way to plan dissemination and promotional activities carried out by the project partners will be planned throughout the entire project duration.

2. Objectives

LoCloud is co-funded by the European Commission ICT PSP programme, it started on 1st March 2013 and runs for three years. The LoCloud consortium consists of 32 partners from 28 countries.

LoCloud aims to support **small and medium-sized institutions** in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by exploring the potential of **cloud computing Technologies**.

LoCloud's main goal is to facilitate the role of small and medium-sized institutions by:

- Supporting them in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by using the cloud to provide services and tools, which help to reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers.
- Making available cloud-based software services which enable them to render their content more discoverable and interoperable.
- Enabling smaller institution types such as house museums, which currently fall outside most aggregation infrastructures, to contribute their content to Europeana.
- Exploring the potential of cloud computing for aggregation, enrichment and re-use, with a special focus on geographic location.
- Exploration and trial of a cloud based architecture as a scalable platform for Europeana metadata aggregation and harvesting with higher efficiency and reduced maintenance costs.
- Provide guidance, training and support facilities to serve the needs of content providers.

The aim of WP6 (**Dissemination and exploitation**) is to organise a large-scale dissemination effort in order to:

- Increase **Europeana's impact at the local level** through a range of activities such as regional, national and international events, online networking and a competition.
- **Promote the availability of LoCloud's results** and available services to small and medium sized institutions and to aggregators throughout Europe.
- Plan and create a **business model** for a sustainable support service for small and medium sized institutions with limited or no access to the Europeana ecosystem.
- Plan with Europeana the way in which the services created by LoCloud can be applied to the whole Europeana corpus in order to **create location-based views** over its entire index.

3. Responsibilities for dissemination activities

WP6 leader is the **University of York - Archaeology Data Service (UoY/ADS)** which is responsible for the following activities:

- Coordination of presentations and poster sessions at relevant European and international conferences by project partners, with the purpose of promoting the results of the LoCloud project.
- Organisation of a LoCloud workshop at an international conference during year two of the project to promote the goals of the project.
- Organisation of a workshop at an international conference during year three to promote the results of the project.

As from April 2014 MDR Partners withdrew from the project. 2Culture associates, with support from NRA, is now responsible for the activities below:

- Establishing and maintaining the LoCloud web site (including design of project logo), coordinating the dissemination of news and information about the project through various channels (e.g. web site and social networks).
- Preparing a LoCloud newsletter to be published in English twice a year.
- Preparing templates for project presentations, documents, briefing papers and other materials.
- Establishing a stakeholder database.
- Producing an initial dissemination plan, an interim and a final dissemination report.

Finally, NRA, with support from 2Culture Associate, will be responsible for the organisation of a Europe-wide competition, at the end of the project to stimulate best practice and innovation amongst individual regions, in creating a 'view' in Europeana of the history and heritage of their locality.

All partners are responsible for disseminating information about the project at conferences, events and workshops, and via news and social media.

All partners are responsible for naming a dissemination lead person who will be responsible for reporting on dissemination activities, for contributing to the development of the project dissemination plan, Interim and Final Dissemination reports, etc.

4. Stakeholder community

WP6 activities aim to raise awareness about LoCloud and its results amongst the following stakeholders:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations.
- Organisations with an interest in cloud computing applied to small and medium sized institutions, such as small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, national and domain aggregation services, holders of private collections, Europeana, and others.
- The Research Community with an interest and involvement in cloud computing in general and, applied, in particular to cultural institutions.
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme.
- Europeana, end users of Europeana (e.g. students, researchers, etc).

One of the objectives of LoCloud is to improve the interoperability of content from localities across Europe from institutional domains which act separately in some countries: namely the 'heritage' sector, and the museum, library and archive sectors, in order to provide a more coherent 'view' of the history and heritage of a given locality.

Geographic location is one of the most important aspects of information about local history and archaeological monuments. It offers a means to reconnect monuments with objects discovered during excavations now held in museum collections and with archives, along with original artworks and publications created by archaeologists, historians, creative writers, artists and ordinary members of the public. The work of LoCloud in this area will help provide end users of Europeana with a gradual but visible improvement in coherence of the 'view' they are able to obtain of the local history of a given locality, often composed of material from a diverse range of sources. All stakeholders, internal and external will substantially benefit from this.

In this connection, the competition to be organised by LoCloud in the final year, will aim to promote innovative use of the LoCloud services, Europeana API etc. in creating a digital 'view' of the culture of their locality or region. This competition will be aligned within the framework of more general dissemination initiatives conducted by the European Commission and by Europeana.

4.1 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are one of the target audiences for the LoCloud project as it is important to disseminate to policy makers within the partner organisations, and to staff or groups within the organisations to be aware of the projects activities and results and to share the news with their contacts.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- progress of project activities;
- results in the more technical areas of the project work, e.g.: cloud technologies, metadata, micro-services;

- standards and guidelines;
- releases of new content in Europeana;
- conferences and other events.

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make the subjects aware of LoCloud and its activities, and to spread the news to their contacts.

Internal stakeholders will be reached during internal meetings through presentations of the project activities and dissemination of news.

4.2 Small and medium sized institutions

Small and medium sized institutions (e.g. local archives, museums, libraries) are the main target of LoCloud. Many small, local institutions have limited IT infrastructure and lack either the requisite staff skills in digitisation and digital libraries or the organisational capacity to obtain large-scale external funding. Despite this, their collections are important and interesting in the context of Europeana and its users. Increasingly, if gradually, these collections are being made available online, and therefore have the potential to contribute to Europeana.

LoCloud will help these institutions make their content available to Europeana, through developing cloud-based software services and micro-services, such as geo-location which are of key importance for local content.

In addition to small and medium sized institutions, the following related stakeholders will be targeted:

- national and domain aggregation services;
- holders of private digital collections;
- Any other institution with an interest in LoCloud activities and in contributing their content to Europeana.

This community is likely to be interested in:

- progress of project work;
- specific research outcomes;
- briefing papers providing guidelines and requirements for inclusion of digital collections into Europeana.

LoCloud will interact with these institutions via several channels, including specific surveys to identify digital collections, distribution of news, participation in events, etc.

4.3 Research community and cloud computing companies / providers

This is the community of researchers, and companies and providers who are active in the field of cloud computing for the cultural heritage sector.

The community is likely to be interested in:

- specific research outcomes;
- the technologies and services being developed in LoCloud;
- needs and requirements of the cultural heritage institutions;
- standards and guidelines;
- business models;
- participation in conferences and events.

LoCloud will interact with this stakeholder community by making use of social channels, by disseminating news, and by making materials available on the project website.

4.4 European Commission

The European Commission is an important stakeholder in the outcomes of the LoCloud project and represents both an opportunity to disseminate project outcomes to policy makers, and also provide dissemination channels to related projects funded by the programme.

The European Commission, its staff and news channels are likely to be interested in news about:

- the results and outcomes of the project;
- delivery of content to Europeana;
- standards and guidelines;
- evaluation of the results.

The LoCloud project will aim to take advantage of opportunities to present the outcomes at events organised by the European Commission. The LoCloud team will take part in collaborative events organised by the European Commission to share results with other funded projects. These will be also reached through direct contacts, participation in international events and other dissemination channels (see section 6).

4.5 Clustering with other projects

LoCloud's initial plan is to liaise with Europeana Cloud¹, Europeana Creative² and Europeana Inside³. This will be done via exchange of news and other forms of collaborations and, in particular, by the participation in the 'Cloud Coordination Group' organised by Europeana Cloud. The aim of this group is to coordinate those projects working on cloud-based applications for the storage, retrieval and manipulation of metadata and digital content within the context of Europeana.

The first virtual meeting of this group was held in June 2013 and there will be several to follow on a regular basis.

The LoCloud project will also closely collaborate with the 3D ICONS project and will be based on the completed CARARE⁴ project. The infrastructural model developed by CARARE and used by 3D ICONS, involving the MINT ingestion service and the MoRe repository, will be the fundamental basis upon which LoCloud's work is being developed.

Throughout the project, LoCloud will be in regular contact with and closely collaborate with Europeana⁵, as LoCloud is a member of the Europeana group of projects. The Europeana office maintains the Europeana group web site (<http://group.europeana.eu>) and disseminates information about projects, including LoCloud, to its stakeholder community through the website, a quarterly newsletter and its news channel. The office also maintains a calendar of events informing group members about upcoming events, inviting participation in clustering activities and disseminating information about project's participation in international conferences and events

The LoCloud team will follow the projects identified above and any other related project, via their websites, Twitter and the other social networks.

4.6 Groups and associations

A number of LoCloud partners are members of groups and associations, which are active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. LoCloud continues to explore opportunities to disseminate news and information about project activities with these groups.

The groups and associations which have been identified so far are:

- WGs of the National Council of Library Coordination
<http://www.mcu.es/bibliotecas/MC/ConsejoCB/Presentacion.html>
- National Association of Archivists and Librarians <http://www.anabad.org/>

¹ <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-cloud>

² <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-creative>

³ <http://www.europeana-inside.eu/home/index.html>

⁴ <http://www.carare.eu>

⁵ <http://pro.europeana.eu>

- Spanish Federation of Societies of Archivists, Librarians and museum professionals (FESABID) <http://www.fesabid.org/en/introduction-of-fesabid>

More groups and associations will be identified in the course of the project and appropriately used as dissemination channels.

4.7 Stakeholder database

The LoCloud project web site provides a functionality, which enables stakeholders from the domain to register to receive the project newsletter. This has enabled the building of a contact database, which will continue to be enlarged throughout the project.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include clustering with other projects, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through various channels including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, and by participating in conferences and events.

5. Dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials was produced for the project and includes:

Project logo

5.1 Project logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher and approved by the project consortium.

5.2 Project website

The LoCloud web site (<http://www.locloud.eu/>) was launched in March 2013. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects, and also to provide an Intranet for members of the project consortium.

Register Login

LoCloud

About News Resources Activities Community

About LoCloud [Read More](#)

LoCloud is a Best Practice Network co-funded under the CIP ICT-PSP programme of the European Commission which will enrich the Europeana content by adding over 4 million digitised items from European cultural institutions.

http://www.locloud.eu/rss/feed/my_feed

Latest News [See All](#)

Jun 05 2013 [Europeana First Free iPad App](#)

May 27 2013 [MTSR 2013](#)

May 19 2013 [Europeana providers](#)

Upcoming Events [See All](#)

Jun 26 2013 [Cultural Heritage, Creative Tools](#)

Jun 27 2013 [IEEE CLOUD 2013](#)

Sep 02 2013 [IPRES-2013](#)

The public areas of the web site include:

- About - the project, consortium and activities
- News – news bulletins and newsletter
- Resources – presentations by project partners, publications, dissemination materials, links to related projects and initiatives
- Activities - Events
- Community – links to the social networks
- How to join – a section providing information for small and medium size institutions willing to join LoCloud
- Contacts

The project Intranet currently includes:

- Work packages (one folder for each of the 7 WPs)
- Reporting
- Reviews
- Deliverables

The web site is made available in English. Where appropriate, project partners may provide translations of some parts of the public pages of the site in their national languages.

5.3 Project newsletter

The project newsletter is produced twice a year. The first three editions were issued in August 2013, February and August 2014 and are available from this link: <http://www.locloud.eu/News/Newsletter>.

The Newsletters are created with a summary newsletter distributed to email lists and with the full newsletter being uploaded to the project website. Notices about the newsletter are posted on the Social networks and by project partners on their email lists. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website.

5.4 Other dissemination materials

A basic set of promotional materials has been prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners for use in dissemination materials
- A project fact sheet
- A LoCloud PowerPoint presentation template.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the LoCloud website.

1.1.1 Videos

A video about the LoCloud project has been developed and made available on the project web site. The video provides an introduction to the project and services.

During the coming months, a set of videos illustrating the LoCloud microservices will be produced and made available on the web site. These will contribute to promoting the services, by explaining their use and benefits for small cultural institutions.

5.5 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications clearly acknowledge the EU funding, through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag (see below).

Example: "This project is co-funded under the ICT Policy Support Programme (ICT PSP) as part of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme by the European Community" (ideally with a link to the ICT PSP website: http://ec.europa.eu/ict_psp).

Any communication or publication states that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

6. Dissemination channels

LoCloud will use a number of channels to disseminate information about the project to its stakeholders.

Our strategy is to approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

The type of message used to transmit information may vary according to the target audience, the phase of the project, and the type of information being promoted. While in the initial phase the dissemination was more focused on encouraging general awareness about the project, in the course of the project, the emphasis will be more on the promotion of the results and achievements of the project's work.

6.1 Project web site and partners web sites

The project web site is the basic dissemination channel of the project. The web site is managed through a Content Management System (CMS) which allows for flexibility in creating / modifying sections and for publication of information and documentation. The dynamic sections of the site are the News and Events.

All partners are encouraged to disseminate information of LoCloud activities and progress on their own institutional web sites, by regularly posting news and providing links to relevant documentation.

6.2 Mailing lists

The project partners are registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different subjects in the cultural heritage, research and business domains and have different memberships.

In the coming months partners will be asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made to enable coordination of the project dissemination to these lists, with the aim of guaranteeing coverage and avoiding duplication.

This will allow the dissemination team to post notices about LoCloud to the lists (for example the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the web site and allow contacts the opportunity to register and receive a copy of the Newsletter directly.

Notices are sent periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The email lists which have been used so far are:

- THEEUROPEANLIBRARY@LIST.ECOMPASS.NL
- EUROPEANA-COMMUNICATORS@LIST.ECOMPASS.NL
- JISCDIGITALMEDIA
- MUSEUMS-INFO (JISC)

- Jisc ADS-ALL
- Foro para profesionales de bibliotecas y documentacion (Forum for library and documentation professionals) (<http://www.rediris.es/list/info/iwetel.html>)
- PUBLICA <http://www.rediris.es/list/info/publicas.html> (public libraries)
- E-learning Special Interest Group Mailing list - elearn@infoserv.inist.fr
- EDTECH on H-Net - EDTECH@H-NET.MSU.EDU
- <http://www.rediris.es/list/info/iwetel.html> (libraries and documentation)
- <http://www.mcu.es/suscripciones/loadAlertForm.do?cache=init&layout=alertasLibro&language=es> (cultural contents from Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport)
- <http://directoriomuseos.mcu.es/dirmuseos/eldirectorio.jsp> (List of museums and collections in Spain, with 1563 institutions included)

6.3 Social networks

We consider Twitter a very effective and fast means of dissemination, for its ease of use and its immediacy, which encourages involvement of a large number of users, so it has been used as much as possible. LinkedIn will also be used to create and maintain a discussion group for topics concerning LoCloud, Europeana and relevant projects. With regard to Facebook, our strategy is to follow the pages on Facebook of other projects (e.g. Europeana Cloud, and CARARE) and not to have a Facebook group for LoCloud, which we may decide to create in the future if need arises in the course of the project.

Twitter

The planned strategy for Twitter⁶ is to:

- post tweets related to the project's activities (Newsletter, events, project progresses) or information related to domains of interest to LoCloud;
- encourage the partners to share interesting news and then tweet them;
- monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag;
- involve LoCloud project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around LoCloud by Tweeting about the project and retweeting any tweets of interest;
- include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website;
- follow lists of relevant Twitter users. This activity will give the LoCloud project visibility: some of these users might follow @LoCloudProject in return or retweet LoCloud tweets to their followers etc.

Our list of relevant Twitter contacts currently includes :

- @Ariadne_Network
- @3DIcons

⁶ <https://twitter.com/LoCloudProject>

- @DavidHaskiya - Product developer at Europeana
- @europeana_cloud
- @eCreativeEU
- @Europeanaeu
- @EuropeanaInside
- @EuropeanaIPR
- @EuropeanaTech
- @Europeana1914
- [@OpenGLAM.](#)

LinkedIn

The strategy for LinkedIn is to promote discussion about project activities and related themes such as cloud computing, metadata, geographic location, etc. News posted to Twitter are republished on LinkedIn. The objective is to increase the number of followers of the group over time.

A group has been established for LoCloud at: http://www.linkedin.com/groups/LoCloud-4984888?home=&gid=4984888&trk=anet_ug_hm.

Our strategy is to involve the members in discussions around the project.

YouTube

A YouTube channel has been established for LoCloud to enable the publication of videos about the project and its activities.

Slideshare

A LoCloud account has been created on Slideshare where all presentations made by partners about LoCloud are uploaded.

6.4 Press releases

Press notices and press release are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release will be prepared and released to announce the launch of the LoCloud competition and further press releases will be prepared to promote key results of LoCloud.

7. Dissemination activities

7.1 Potential national and international events

During recent months, LoCloud partners have participated in a substantial number of national and international events (see Annex 1) in the local heritage and professional domains with the aim of promoting the results of the project and to advocate the contribution of content/metadata to Europeana.

In the coming months LoCloud will more closely coordinate presentations, poster sessions and workshops at key conferences, for the purpose of promoting the results of the project and the contribution of content to Europeana. It will also be represented at events organised by related projects and at clustering events organised by the Commission.

A series of events have been identified by partners as being relevant to the stakeholder communities targeted by the LoCloud dissemination strategy.

Below the list of conferences and meetings that are potential venues for dissemination.

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
CIDOC-Conference 2014	http://www.cidoc2014.de/index.php/en/	Annual conference of CIDOC, the International Committee for Documentation of ICOM	Dresden, Germany	7-11 September 2014
European Association for Archaeology (EAA)	https://www.eaa2014istanbul.org	International Archaeology conference held yearly.	Istanbul, Turkey	10-14 September 2014
Kai-Konferanse	http://www.arkivinordland.no/Filnedlasting.aspx?Mid1=605&Fillid=24290	National conference	Bodø, Norway	16-18 September 2014
URLA 2014: International Congress on Management of Cultural Heritage and Cultural Memory Institutions	URLA 2014: International Congress on Management of Cultural Heritage and Cultural Memory Institutions	Organised every year by the University and Research Librarians' Association in Turkey (URLA) to raise awareness amongst practitioners on information services, information & document management, knowledge economy, information literacy, industrialization of information, etc.	Istanbul, Turkey	17-20 September 2014
Annual meeting of the Agency for Culture	http://www.kulturstyrelsen.dk/om-kulturstyrelsen/moeder-og-konferencer/kulturstyrelsens-aarsmoede-2014/	Annual meeting of the Agency for Culture	Nyborg, Denmark	22-23 September 2014
Europeana Projects	http://www.eventbrite.co	Assembly of all Europeana-related	The Hague,	25-26 September

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Group Assembly	uk/e/europeana-projects-group-assembly-registration-1-212701786385	projects	Netherlands	2014
Usage of Cloud technologies in libraries	http://www.fondacijanb.rs/cms/view.php?id=1007	National seminar focused on cloud technologies applied to libraries	Belgrade, Serbia	1 October 2014
Geomatika v projektech 2014	http://gis.zcu.cz/?page=geomatika-v-projektech	National conference	Kozel, Czech Republic	1-2 October 2014
Conference of National Association of Librarians	http://www.anbpr.org.ro/index.php/stiri/660-conferin%C5%A3a-na%C5%A3ional%C4%83-a-anbpr-biblionext-%E2%80%93-bibliotecile-publice-%E2%80%93-motorul-dezvolt%C4%83rii-durabile-a-comunit%C4%83%C5%A3ilor	Annual conference of National Association of Librarians	Targu Jiu, Romania	9-10 October 2014
BAM, conference of libraries, archives and museums	http://www.bam.ba/index.php/en/konferencija-bam/bam-2014	Organised by the Association of Information professionals (BAM) this is a conference for libraries, archives and museums	Sarajevo, Bosnia	10-11 October 2014
Archives and Cultural Industries	http://www.girona.cat/web/ica2014/eng/index.php	The event groups together the 2nd Annual Conference of the International Council on Archives, the 9th European Conference on Archives, and the 13th Image and	Girona, Spain	11-15 October 2014

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		Research Seminar.		
Samdok Konferanse 2014	http://samdok.com/nytt-fra-prosjektene/locloud/	LoCloud workshop at national conference	Oslo, Norway	15-16 October 2014
ISWC 2014	http://iswc2014.semanticweb.org/	ISWC 2014 is the premier international forum for the Semantic Web / Linked Data Community.	Riva del Garda, Italy	19-23 October 2014
The European Conference on Information Literacy (ECIL2014)	http://www.ecil2014.org/	The European Conference on Information Literacy (or ECIL2014) is organized by the Department of Information Management of Hacettepe University and Department of Information and Communication Sciences of Zagreb	Dubrovnik Croatia	20-23 October 2014
Euromed2014	http://www.culturalheritage2014.eu/	This 5th edition of EuroMed2014 aims to bring together researchers, policy makers, professionals and practitioners to discuss and explore key issues related to the management and conservation of cultural heritage.	Limassol, Cyprus	3-8 November 2014
ICOMOS Scientific Symposium	http://florence2014.icomos.org/	The Symposium will focus on the following themes. <i>Main theme:</i> Heritage and Landscape as Human Values <i>Sub-themes</i> 1 Sharing and experiencing the identity of communities through	Florence, Italy	10-14 November 2014

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		tourism and interpretation 2 Landscape as cultural habitat 3 Sustainability through traditional knowledge 4 Community driven conservation and local empowerment 5 Emerging tools for conservation practice		
Second national conference MAB (musei, archivi biblioteche)	http://www.mab-italia.org/	Second national conference MAB for libraries, museums, archives (musei, archivi biblioteche)	Rome, Italy	20-21 November 2014
International Workshop on Research Data Management	http://rdm.bilgiyonetimi.net/index.html		Ankara, Turkey	21 November 2014
IMCW2014. 5th International Symposium on Information Management in a Changing World	http://imcw2014.bilgiyonetimi.net/	The International Conference on Knowledge Management (ICKM) provides researchers and practitioners from all over the world a forum for discussion and exchange of ideas concerning theoretical and practical aspects of Knowledge Management	Antalya, Turkey	24-26 November 2014
10th International Conference on Knowledge Management	http://ickm2014.bilgiyonetimi.net/	This event, jointly held with IMCW2014 provides researchers and practitioners from all over the world a forum for discussion and exchange of ideas concerning theoretical and practical aspects of Knowledge Management	Antalya, Turkey	24-26 November 2014

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Archives, Libraries, Museums in the Digital World 2014	http://www.skipcr.cz/akce-a-projekty/akce-skip/archivy-knihovny-muzea-v-digitalnim-svete/15.-konference-archivy-knihovny-muzea-v-digitalnim-svete-2014	National event held every year in Czech Republic	Prague, Czech Republic	26-27 November 2014
Seminar Archives, Libraries, Museums - Global and Local - GLOCAL		Annual national conference with International speakers	Rovinj, Croatia	26-28 November 2014
8th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research (MTSR'14)	http://www.mtsr-conf.org/	The eighth International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research (MTSR'14) aims to bring together scholars and practitioners that share a common interest in the interdisciplinary field of metadata, linked data and ontologies.	Karlsruhe, Germany	27-29 November 2014
County Head Library Education - LoCloud Collections Workshop	Not available	Regional - County Libraries Meeting	Mali Lošinj, Croatia	December 2014
SWIB14	http://swib.org/swib14/	The SWIB conference aims to provide substantial information on Linked Open Data developments relevant to the library world and to foster the exchange of ideas and experiences among practitioners.		1 December 2014
Málþing á afmælisdegi dr. Kristjáns Eldjárns.	Not available	National seminar gathering representatives of libraries and	Reykjavík,	6 December 2014

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		museums	Iceland	
Preserving small nation's identity in EU - libraries position and role	www.gkmm.hr	National conference devoted to the role of libraries in Croatia	Split, Croatia	15 December 2014
International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)	tbd	The International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL) constitutes a leading scientific forum on digital libraries that brings together researchers, developers, content providers and users in the field of digital libraries.	TBD	2015
ICCHT 2015: XII International Conference on Cultural Heritage and Tourism	https://www.waset.org/conference/2015/01/paris/ICCHT	The event aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results about all aspects of Cultural Heritage and Tourism.	Paris, France	23-24 January 2015
Digital Libraries conference	http://conference.ait.co.at/digbib/index.php/	Annual event devoted to all aspects of digital libraries	Graz, Austria	23-25 February 2015
Computer Applications in Archaeology	http://caaconference.org/	The 43rd Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology "Conference (CAA 2015 SIENA) will explore a multitude of topics to showcase ground-breaking technologies and best practice from various archaeological and computer sciences disciplines.	Siena, Italy	30 March-2 April 2015
5th Festival of Croatian	http://dfest.nsk.hr/	National event	Zagreb, Croatia	April 2015

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Digitisation Project				
Student scientific conference 2015		National scientific conference	Bratislava, Slovakia	April 2015
LINQ Conference - Learning Innovations and Quality	www.learning-innovations.eu	Annual International conference gathering experts, practitioners and interested stakeholders in the fields of lifelong learning, education and training from Europe and all countries	Amsterdam or Brussels (tbc)	11-15 May 2015
BLIA Annual Conference	http://www.lib.bg	Annual Conference organised by the Bulgarian Library and Information Association	Sofia, Bulgaria	11-12 June 2015
European Association for Archaeology (EAA)	http://eaaglasgow2015.com/	The EAA will contribute to the cultural legacy of Scotland's great year of celebrations (2014). The event will welcome around 2,000 delegates to celebrate the EAA's 21st Annual Meeting at the EAA Glasgow 2015 and look forward to sharing Scotland's rich and unique cultural heritage.	Glasgow, Scotland	2-5 September 2015
ICDH 2015: XIII International Conference on Digital Heritage	http://www.waset.org/conference/2015/11/london/ICDH	The conference aims to bring together leading academic scientists, researchers and research scholars to exchange and share their experiences and research results about all aspects of Digital Heritage.	London, UK	27-28 November 2015

7.2 Potential Journals

Journal	Country	Link	Description
Historicka revue	Slovakia	http://www.historickarevue.com	A scientific-popular journal about history and archaeology.
Muzeum	Slovakia	http://www.snm.sk/?casopis-muzeum	Guidance, information and study review for museum and art gallery workers.
Naša Univerzita	Slovakia	http://www.uniba.sk/?nu	The Journal of the Comenius University.
Zprávy památkové péče	Czech Republic		Professional journal in Czech language with English and German summary, issued by the National Heritage Institute and focused on heritage and conservation.
Boletín de la Anabad Bulletin of the National Association of Archivists and Librarians	Spain	http://www.anabad.org/publicaciones/boletin.html	Professional journal covering theoretical and practical topics related to archives and libraries.
Delibros Magazine on publishing sector	Spain	http://www.delibros.com/login	Related to the world of publishers, It includes a section on libraries.
Boletín SMS (Somos museos)	Spain		Newsletter of the Unit for the State Museums. It contains news, policies and activities related to Spanish state museums.
Noticias BAD	Portugal	http://www.bad.pt/noticia	Online publication of the Portuguese Association of Librarians, Archivists and Documentalists. It targets professionals working within the archives, libraries and museums fields.
Philobiblon Revue	Romania	http://www.philobiblon.ro/	Transylvanian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Humanities
Jlis.it	Italy	http://leo.cilea.it/index.php/jlis/	Italian Journal of Library and information science, is

			an academic journal of international scope, peer-reviewed and open access, aiming to valorise international research in Library and Information Science.
Almanacco Bibliografico	Italy	http://centridiricerca.unicatt.it/cr/eleb_173.html	quarterly bulletin of the Università Cattolica in Milan related to the history of libraries and books.
Bibliothecae.it	Italy	http://www.bibliothecae.it/index.php?page=abbonamenti	italian half-year journal in history of libraries and books.
AIB Notizie	Italy	http://www.aib.it/pubblicazioni/aib-notizie/	Bimonthly bulletin of Italian libraries Association .
Digitalia. Rivista del digitale nei Beni Culturali	Italy	http://digitalia.sbn.it	Magazine on the application of digital technologies to cultural heritage, published since 2005 by the ICCU.
Information Technology and Libraries	Australia	http://ejournals.bc.edu/ojs/index.php/ital/index	Publishes materials related to all aspects of information technology in all types of libraries. Topic areas include, but are not limited to, library automation, digital libraries, metadata, distributed systems and networks, computer security, intellectual property rights, geographic information systems, and many others.
Archives and Museum Informatics	International	http://www.springer.com/new+%26+forthcoming+titles+%28default%29/journal/10505	Archives and Museum Informatics is an international forum for the representation of knowledge and the management of information relating to the world's cultural heritage. It presents timely, technical contributions to cultural informatics, including theory, case studies of implementations, and reviews standards, print and electronic publications, software, network sites

			and conferences.
ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)	International	http://jocch.acm.org/	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage.
International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE)	International	http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage, Digital Libraries and Archives.
International Journal for Innovation and Quality and in Learning (INNOQUAL)	International	http://innoqual.efquel.org/	The International Journal for Innovation and Quality and in Learning (INNOQUAL) is an open access, open peer-reviewed journal providing an international perspective on the theory and practice of innovation and quality in the field of learning at all educational levels and in all training contexts. It seeks contributions which discuss how technology can contribute to innovate and enhance the quality of learning.
International Journal of the Inclusive Museum	International	http://onmuseums.com/publications/journal	The International Journal of the Inclusive Museum brings together academics, curators, museum and public administrators, cultural policy makers and research students to engage in discussions about the historic character and future shape of the museum. The key question of the Journal is: How can the institution of the museum become more inclusive?

7.2 LoCloud planned events

Meeting/event	Date (Project month)	Participants	Location
Mid-term plenary meeting	28-29 November 2013	All participants	London, UK
Regional training workshops	23/24 October 20/21 November 11/12 December	Selected partners	Gironde, France Poznań, Poland Graz, Austria
Workshop at international conference: ICOMOS General Assembly	11 November 2014	Project Management, technical partners	Florence, Italy
LoCloud hackathon or competition presentation at EuropeanaTech Conference	12-13 February 2015	Selected partners	tbc
Mid-term plenary meeting	11 February 2015	All participants	Paris, France (tbc)
Workshop at international conference	M24-36	Selected partners	Tbc
Second and final technical reviews	M24 & M36	Project management team, WP leaders	Tbd
Final conference and awards	M34-36	Up to 200 external stakeholders, plus project participants	Tbd

8. Conclusion

This document presents the dissemination strategy of the LoCloud project for the first two years.

In the first year dissemination activities focussed on raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts.

This dissemination plan will be updated by month 24 to produce the Interim Dissemination Report.

9. Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines

Guidelines for Tweeting About the LoCloud Project

2Culture associates manages the Twitter account of the LoCloud project (@LoCloudProject).

The LoCloud project members are invited to Tweet about the project or retweet any tweets of interest. In order to make the best use of Twitter for the Project the following guidelines will be of help.

1. Target audience The prime focus should be people from Cultural Heritage organisations/institutions, especially small and medium sized institutions. After this, it should be aimed at professionals (not necessary working in the field on Cultural Heritage) involved in /with experience in cloud computing technologies.

2. Objectives for Twitter:

- a. Keep key followers informed of LoCloud activities (progress made, publications, upcoming events etc.)
- b. Inform followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to LoCloud.

3. Achieving the objectives:

- a. Informing followers about new content on the LoCloud web site and LinkedIn.
- b. Informing followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to LoCloud (i.e. upcoming conferences/prizes/info days/calls/research areas/innovations/studies)

4. Tweets posted: Twitter only allows tweets of 140 characters or less, tweets should include a link with a title (to effectively communicate the message) and in some cases use a more confidential tone.

5. LoCloud follows – people who are related to the target audience and professionally involved in cloud computing and cultural heritage. We do not follow people whose tweets are of a personal nature. We will periodically review and ‘unfollow’ the less useful tweeters to make monitoring the feeds more manageable.

6. Tweeting: it would be useful to Tweet at least once a fortnight

7. Reply: The LoCloud account will reply to specific tweets directed at @LoCloud (asking questions or feedback about the project).

LoCloud Project members (and followers):

- remember to use the hash tag when you are tweeting about the project: #LoCloud
- Please Retweet any tweets that may of interest to your friends and colleagues

10. Appendix II: Guidelines for partners

Guidelines for partners of LoCloud regarding their dissemination activities

Where to find LoCloud promotional materials

Dissemination materials for use by LoCloud partners are available in the Partners area of the web site, under WP6, at:

<http://www.locloud.eu/Partner-Area/WP6-Dissemination-and-exploitation>

This section will be regularly updated throughout the project.

Where to disseminate information about LoCloud

All project partners are requested to promote LoCloud whenever possible, namely:

- on their institutional website
- at national and international events (organised by their own institutions, by other institutions, by Europeana, or by other Europeana group projects, etc.)
- at relevant professional fairs and exhibitions.

Production of customised promotional materials

Partners who wish to produce customized promotional material for dissemination in their country (for example, in the language of their country) can do that using their own budget.

Note that all dissemination materials should comply with the corporate image of the project and thus before producing any materials partners should contact 2Culture Associates.

All project dissemination materials must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag (see paragraph 5.5).

Informing and reporting on your dissemination activities

Before the event:

Each partner should inform UoY/ADS and 2Culture of any event they plan to attend indicating the name of the event, dates location, URL and planned contribution (e.g. presentation, poster session, etc.). This will enable the LoCloud management to coordinate dissemination activities, avoiding overlaps and WP6 leaders to promote the event and the partner's contribution on the project web site and other dissemination channels.

Partners are also expected to promote their dissemination efforts on their own web sites, via project and professional mailing lists, personal contacts, social networks, press releases, etc.

After the event:

All partners should report on their dissemination activities via using the available reporting template which includes a section on dissemination (available in the Partner area of the project web site at: <http://www.locloud.eu/Partner-Area/Reporting>).

Partners are also encouraged to send their delivered presentations (in pdf format), audios, videos, images, or any other related materials to Barbara Morganti (mail@barbaramorganti.org) for publication on the LoCloud website.